

POLICY BRIEF

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NEW TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: CAN WE CHANGE THE REALITY OF THE POOREST COUNTRIES?

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POLICY STATEMENT

Today, the advancement of new technologies has directly and indirectly impacted society around the world, with a focus on the field of information. Innovation and automation lead subjects of the most different socioeconomic and cultural backgrounds to constant or instantaneous changes, depending on the context and need, as in countries during COVID-19's health crisis when public and private institutions shifted rapidly. In this light, the question that prompts this essay is: How can new technologies and uses of artificial intelligence benefit poorer countries? At the time that we are asking this question, we reflect that it will be a challenge for all countries, particularly the richest ones, as the new technologies have also been creating social disparities, resulting in varying impacts, which has led to a more critical outlook on the new scenarios that are unfolding.

BACKGROUND

To analyze this process, we can quickly recall that societies have experienced technological revolutions/disruptions in each period (centuries that have passed), resulting in various consequences and impacts on their infrastructures and socio-political aspects, respectively. In the Industrial Revolution, as manufacturing replaced mechanical work and steam engines and machines were adopted at the end of the 19th century, the political and social consequences were profound. A clear division between labor and capital made our society change from a state-based to a class-based society, and the division between them impacted our political and cultural history. As well as steel, heavy and war engineering, household appliances, and heavy industry dominated the 20th century. Our economy faces the peak of financial and monopoly capital, income concentration, and consumer society on the socioeconomic level.

Information technology was fundamental for industry automation, highway construction, and airports in the last decades of the twentieth century. As a result, we are feeling the rapid obsolescence of technology. Regarding social impacts, technologies have become elitist, deepening social inequalities through the extinction of jobs and the mass unemployment of vulnerable workers. Nations, organizations, and leading intellectuals began to discuss the impacts of globalization and neoliberalism on countries, especially the poorest and most backward, from an economic point of view.

Artificial intelligence and the convergence of digital, physical, and biological technologies have enabled us to advance in the 21st century. The internet, email, and other tools allow individuals to interact almost instantly. Additionally, digital platforms, different business formats, and higher costs were incorporated. There has been a significant reduction in distance in discussions relating to practical, ethical, ideological, and political issues. However, tensions remain regarding the use and control of these technologies, particularly in the military.

FINDINGS

Technological innovations and their consequences have created possibilities for new paradigm propagation and generalization over the years. However, research indicates that countries that did not promote technological advancements and adjust to new paradigms lag behind. Sen emphasizes the dramatic condition of people whose access to different spheres of life is limited. According to Sen: "Being poor does not only imply material hardship. Poverty can be defined as a deprivation of basic necessities and not just as an income below a pre-established threshold." (1).

Since 1980, several United Nations (UN) international organizations have accepted poverty as relative deprivation with a broader, more scientific perspective on its social component. As a result, economically developing or undeveloped nations have challenges overcoming limited access to basic necessities like food, housing, health care, and inferior technology. Even if the topic of changing technologies and their application in various nations is evident, it is important to stress that it is unfair that certain cultures have the benefit of technical dominance while others remain entirely outside of the mainstream of global advancement.

A team of researchers from the International Monetary Fund draws the world's attention to these disparities when they argue that shifting more investments to advanced economies where automation is already established, particularly with technologies, threatens the social and political balance between poor and rich countries (2). According to Carlos Arboleta, Deputy Resident Representative of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) in Brazil: "Faced with this new reality, we urgently need to discuss profound issues such as ethics, property and how it is used so that it does not become a tool for expanding inequalities, within or between countries" (3).

For instance, the Sustainable Development Objectives (SDGs) are a set of 169 objectives and 17 guiding principles that aim to build a society that upholds principles and values such as equality, health, the environment, and education. Since education is one of the ODS's guiding principles, we comprehend that having access to it is a crucial right for fostering civic engagement and democracy. Artificial intelligence centered on a pedagogical quality culture may be a revolutionary learning tool for students or other interested parties. Multiple applications and interfaces were created during COVID-19, enabling video communication and having a favorable influence on remote education.

AI can design a learning environment tailored to each country's unique requirements and conditions. Women, girls, and vulnerable minorities who face moral and physical assault and live in poverty stand to profit the most from AI. AI can help governments and non-governmental groups create more sustainable societies that promote gender equality via education. A recent post on the UNDP Brazil website

said that an artificial intelligence (AI) tool would be used to help male and female judges and other justice service providers who deal with female homicide cases. The agreement includes the UNDP and the National Council of Justice, and it will be implemented by the Court of Justice of the State of Ceará (TJCE) later this year, in 2023. According to Enfoque Econômico (2019), the region has a death rate from violence against women of 37%, which is higher than the regional and national rates (5; 6). In Brazil and other nations with high levels of poverty and violence, this kind of initiative using AI can inspire other public policies, such as the creation of didactic material and/or in the form of mentoring in the prevention of gender violence to be shared with parents, teachers, community leaders, students, among others, in primary education schools.

CONCLUSIONS

There is no simple solution to using emerging technology, particularly artificial intelligence, to achieve social fairness in developing nations. On the other hand, artificial intelligence (AI) may assist public and corporate organizations in define research and investment objectives in these most vulnerable civilizations. Working groups of technology professionals, government, companies, and social organizations should be formed to mentor NGOs on AI. Case studies, indicators, instructional materials, and courses should be included in these groupings. It is critical to realize that algorithms cannot replace public policymakers. Humans will always be required to examine acquired data. Despite its limitations, AI should not be neglected but adopted for the greater good.

RECOMMENDATIONS

AI is a strong instrument that can help thousands of people in underdeveloped nations overcome poverty and improve their quality of life. To that purpose, the following suggestions might help us think about good public policy using AI:

- (i) The first advice is to focus resources on areas where people's lives may be improved immediately, such as health, education, agriculture, and infrastructure. AI may be used to discover novel medical treatments, offer customized tutoring for students, increase agricultural output efficiency, and build roads and bridges, to name a few applications.
- (ii) Second, collaborating on projects with public and private businesses and international organizations gives people access to resources and knowledge they may not otherwise have. Microsoft, for instance, is collaborating with the Kenyan government to create an AI platform to enhance healthcare and education.
- (iii) Thirdly, investing in education and training will make more skilled employees available in the automated market. For instance, governments and the corporate sector might provide scholarships to students, particularly underprivileged girls, to study STEM subjects.
- (iv) Fostering more responsible AI usage governance is the final step. For instance, the European Union is creating a code of conduct for developing and applying AI.

These suggestions can help developing nations make the most of AI's promise to enhance citizen lives and fight poverty.

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